

A REVIEW ON NANOFORMULATION OF PLANT BASED NATURAL PRODUCTS TARGETING IMPROVED β - CELL FUNCTION IN DIABETES MELLITUS

Reshma B V

Delta Pharmacy, Oman

Abstract:

Herbal remedies are used to manage type 2 diabetes mellitus (type 2 DM) as the sole treatment or as a complementary therapy. Limitations of herbal remedies, such as poor stability and limited absorption, impede their development as therapeutic agents, which could be overcome by nanoformulations. This review attempts to summarize the studies reported between 2009 and 2020 in the development of medicinal plant-based nanoformulations for the management of type 2 DM, discuss formulation methods, mechanisms of action, and identify gaps in the literature to conduct future research on nanoparticle-based herbal treatment options targeting type 2 DM.

Nanoformulations of plant-based natural products improve diabetes management by increasing the bioavailability of plant compounds, which can then improve glycemic control, enhance insulin sensitivity, and protect pancreatic beta-cells. Nanotechnology creates formulations like polymeric nanoparticles and liposomes that encapsulate active compounds, leading to better stability, solubility, and targeted delivery compared to the natural plant extracts alone. To retrieve articles published between January 2009 and December 2020, the electronic databases PubMed, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were searched with the keywords nanoparticle, plant, and diabetes in the entire text. Peer-reviewed research articles on herbal nanoformulations published in English-language based on in vitro and/or in vivo models of type 2 DM and/or its complications were included.

Keywords: herbal remedies; inorganic nanoformulations; lipid-based nanoformulations; polymeric nanoformulations; type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Corresponding author:

Reshma B V,

Delta Pharmacy, Oman

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press Reshma B V ., a review on nanoformulation of plant based natural products targeting improved β - cell function in diabetes mellitus, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(11).

NANOFORMULATION OF PLANT-BASED NATURAL PRODUCTS FOR TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

Among the reported studies, 68% of the studies were on inorganic herbal nanoformulations, whereas 17% and 8% were of polymer-based and lipid-based herbal nanoformulations, respectively. Some of the important biological properties of nanoformulations included improvement in glycemic control and insulin levels, inhibition of the formation of advanced glycation end products, and regeneration of pancreatic β cells.^[1] The aforementioned properties were observed by screening nanoformulations using *in vitro* cellular and noncellular models, as well as *in vivo* animal models of type 2 DM studied for acute or sub-acute durations. Only 2 clinical trials with patients with diabetes were reported, indicating the need for further research on medicinal plant-based nanoformulations as a therapeutic option for the management of type 2 DM. Medicinal plant extracts and isolated compounds have been nanoformulated using various methods^[1]. The properties of the nanoformulations were found superior to those of the corresponding herbal extracts and isolated compounds. At both the preclinical and clinical levels, there are a number of poorly explored research areas in the development and bioactivity assessment of herbal nanoformulations.

HERBAL MEDICINES TARGETING THE IMPROVED β -CELL FUNCTIONS AND β -CELL REGENERATION FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS

There is an increasing trend of investigating natural bioactive compounds targeting pancreatic β -cells for the prevention/treatment of diabetes mellitus (DM). With the exploration of multiple mechanisms by which β -cells involve in the pathogenesis of DM, herbal medicines are gaining attention due to their multitasking ability as evidenced by traditional medicine practices. This review attempts to summarize herbal medicines with the potential for improvement of β -cell functions and regeneration as scientifically proven by *in vivo/in vitro* investigations. Furthermore, attempts have been made to identify the mechanisms of improving the function and regeneration of β -cells by herbal medicines.

Relevant data published from January 2009 to March 2020 were collected by searching electronic databases "PubMed," "ScienceDirect," and "Google Scholar" and studied for this review. Single herbal extracts, polyherbal mixtures, and isolated compounds derived from approximately 110 medicinal plants belonging to 51 different plant families had been investigated in recent years and found to be targeting β -cells. Many herbal medicines showed improvement of β -cell function

as observed through homeostatic model assessment- β -cell function (HOMA- β). Pancreatic β -cell regeneration as observed in histopathological and immunohistochemical studies in terms of increase of size and number of functional β -cells was also prominent. Increasing β -cell mass via expression of genes/proteins related to antiapoptotic actions and β -cell neogenesis/proliferation, increasing glucose-stimulated insulin secretion via activating glucose transporter-2 (GLUT-2) receptors, and/or increasing intracellular Ca^{2+} levels were observed upon treatment of some herbal medicines.

Some herbal medicines acted on various insulin signaling pathways. Furthermore, many herbal medicines showed protective effects on β -cells via reduction of oxidative stress and inflammation. However, there are many unexplored avenues. Thus, further investigations are warranted in elucidating mechanisms of improving β -cell function and mass by herbal medicines, their structure-activity relationship (SAR), and toxicities of these herbal medicines.

NATURAL ALKALOIDS AND DIABETES

MELLITUS

Natural alkaloids and Diabetes Mellitus

The use of herbal therapies for treatment and management of diabetes mellitus and complications associated with this chronic condition is increasing. Plants contain a bounty of phytochemicals that have been proven to be protective by reducing the risk of various ailments and diseases, including alkaloids. Moreover, alkaloids are known to be among the oldest natural products used by humans for highlighting drugs that play crucial roles as therapeutic agents. The reason for this expanding interest and uses of alkaloids as a part of plant natural compounds-based treatments is that a significant proportion of diabetic patients do not

respond very well to conventional therapeutic medication.^[2] Furthermore, other explanations to this fact are the cost of medication, side-effects, accessibility, and availability of health facilities and drugs and the inefficiency of these medicines in certain cases.

In this study we aimed to review the literature on the valuable effects of herbs and plants and their isolated alkaloids compounds as medication for management of diabetes, a prevalent risk factor for several other disorders and illnesses. In the current review, PubMed, ScienceDirect, Springer and google scholar databases were used and the criterion for inclusion was based on the following keywords and phrases: diabetes, hyperglycemia, complications of diabetes, alkaloids, antidiabetic alkaloids, hypoglycemic alkaloids, alkaloids and complications of diabetes mellitus, mechanisms of action and alkaloids.

In the current review, we demonstrate that alkaloids in the form of extracts and isolated molecules obtained from a large variety of species demonstrated their efficiency for improving raises in blood glucose either in animal models via experimental studies or in human subjects via clinical trials. Medicinal species as chillies (*Capsicum annum*), turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), barberry (*Berberis vulgaris*) and cress (*Lepidium sativum*) are among the most common and therapeutic plants used for controlling diabetes that were the subject of several experimental and clinical investigations. Whereas, isolated alkaloids such as berberine, capsaicin and trigonelline have received more interest in this field.^[2] Interestingly, the therapeutic impact of alkaloids against blood glucose pathogenesis is mediated through a variety of signaling cascades and pathways, via inhibiting or stimulating diversity of systems such as inhibition of α -glucosidase enzyme, blockade of PTP- 1B, deactivation of DPP-IV, increasing insulin sensitivity and modulating the oxidative stress. Based on the findings of the present review, alkaloids could be used as preventive and curative agents in the case of endocrine disorders, particularly diabetes and could play a promoting function for the discovery of new antidiabetic agents.

THE USE OF PLANTS IN THE TRADITIONAL MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES : PHARMACOLOGICAL AND TOXICOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The prevalence of diabetes is on a steady increase worldwide and it is now identified as one of the main threats to human health in the 21st century. In Nigeria, the use of herbal medicine alone or alongside prescription drugs for its management is quite common.^[3] We hereby carry out a review of

medicinal plants traditionally used for diabetes management in Nigeria. Based on the available evidence on the species' pharmacology and safety, we highlight ways in which their therapeutic potential can be properly harnessed for possible integration into the country's healthcare system. Ethnobotanical information was obtained from a literature search of electronic databases such as Google Scholar, Pubmed and Scopus up to 2013 for publications on medicinal plants used in diabetes management, in which the place of use and/or sample collection was identified as Nigeria.^[4] 'Diabetes' and 'Nigeria' were used as keywords for the primary searches; and then 'Plant name - accepted or synonyms', 'Constituents', 'Drug interaction' and/or 'Toxicity' for the secondary searches.

The hypoglycemic effect of over a hundred out of the 115 plants reviewed in this paper is backed by preclinical experimental evidence, either in vivo or in vitro. One-third of the plants have been studied for their mechanism of action, while isolation of the bioactive constituent(s) has been accomplished for twenty three plants. Some plants showed specific organ toxicity, mostly nephrotoxic or hepatotoxic, with direct effects on the levels of some liver function enzymes.^[5] Twenty eight plants have been identified as in vitro modulators of P-glycoprotein and/or one or more of the cytochrome P450 enzymes, while eleven plants altered the levels of phase 2 metabolic enzymes, chiefly glutathione, with the potential to alter the pharmacokinetics of co-administered drugs. This review, therefore, provides a useful resource to enable a thorough assessment of the profile of plants used in diabetes management so as to ensure a more rational use. By anticipating potential toxicities or possible herb-drug interactions, significant risks which would otherwise represent a burden on the country's healthcare system can be avoided.

REFERENCES:

1. Nanof ormulation of Plant-Based Natural Products for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: From Formulation Design to Therapeutic Applications Akurange Sujeevi Dammadinna Wickramasinghe¹, Pabasara Kalansuriya², Anoja Priyadarshani Attanayake²
2. Natural Alkaloids and Diabetes Mellitus: A Review Mohammed Ajebli¹, Haroun Khan², Mohamed Eddouks¹
3. Herbal Medicines Targeting the Improved β -Cell Functions and β -Cell Regeneration for the Management of Diabetes Mellitus Akurange Sujeevi Dammadinna Wickramasinghe¹, Pabasara Kalansuriya², Anoja Priyadarshani Attanayake²

4. Diabetes mellitus and its management with medicinal plants: A perspective based on Iranian research. Arezou Rezaei¹, Azad Farzadfard², Atefe Amirahmadi³, Maasoomeh Alemi³, Mitra Khademi⁴
5. The use of plants in the traditional management of diabetes in Nigeria: pharmacological and toxicological considerations. Udoamaka F Ezuruike¹, Jose M Prieto²